

BENZOYL CHLORIDE AS A POLAR SOLVENT. PART II. FORMATION OF ACID-BASE NEUTRALISATION COMPLEXES IN BENZOYL CHLORIDE

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The tetrachlorides of tin, titanium, tellurium and zirconium and antimony pentachloride, which act as solvo-acids in benzoyl chloride, neutralise solvo-bases, quinoline, pyridine, α -picoline and β -picoline, and ansolvo-base, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride, in benzoyl chloride solutions, resulting in the formation of neutralisation complexes. Eighteen such neutralisation complexes have been isolated and the mechanism of these neutralisation reactions has been proposed.

In the light of the studies of the solubilities, solvate formation (Paul, Bains and Singh, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 489) and solvolytic reactions (*ibid.*, under publication) in benzoyl chloride, its ionisation into benzoylium and chloride ions has been proposed as :

On the basis of the modern concept of the theory of solvent systems, substances which on dissolution in benzoyl chloride increase the concentration of benzoylium ions will act as acids and those which increase the concentration of chloride ions will act as bases. Lewis acids, due to their capacity to increase their co-ordination number, take up chloride ions and indirectly increase the concentration of benzoylium ions and, thus, act as solvo-acids. Most of the strongly ionic metal chlorides, which will produce chloride ions, should act as ansolvo-bases in benzoyl chloride. Organic tertiary bases like quinoline, pyridine, etc., which due to the electron-donor property of their nitrogen atoms, combine with the benzoylium ions, indirectly increase the concentration of chloride ions and will therefore act as solvo-bases.

Neutralisation reactions between the tetrachlorides of tin, titanium, tellurium and zirconium and antimony pentachloride as solvo-acids and the ansolvo-base, dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride, and the solvo-bases, quinoline, pyridine, α -picoline and β -picoline, have been studied and as a result, the complexes recorded in Table I have been isolated.

It is clear from Table I that the tetrachlorides of tin, titanium, tellurium and zirconium react with the bases to afford two types of complexes, the normal salts of the general formula $(\text{B.Bz})_2.\text{MCl}_6$ and the acid salts of the general formula $(\text{B.Bz})-\text{Bz.MCl}_6$, where B denotes a tertiary organic base (Bz stands for benzoyl and M, for the metal). The normal salts are produced when the acid solution is added dropwise to the base solution, the quantities of the two being arranged to correspond to a molar ratio of 1:2, while formation of the acid salt is facilitated by adding a solution of the base to that of the acid and their quantities are arranged to be in the molar ratio of 1:1. Some of the complexes can lose the solvent molecules to give rise to desolvated compounds, as will be discussed later with particular reference to the desolvated compounds.

TABLE I
Acid-base neutralisation complex isolated in benzoyl chloride.

S. No.	Name of the complex.	Formula.	Colour.	M.P.	% Cl.		% Metal		% Nitrogen	
					Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1.	bis-Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorostannate.	$[(C_6H_5)_2N.C_6H_5.C_6H_7]_2.SnCl_6$	White	218° (d)	28.40	28.21	15.62	15.71	3.80	3.71
2.	bis-Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorotitanate.	$[(CH_3)_2N.C_6H_5.C_6H_7]_2.TiCl_6$	Deep yellow	102-106°	30.75	31.09	6.98	6.99	...	...
3.	bis-Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorotellurite.	$[(CH_3)_2N.C_6H_5.C_6H_7]_2.TeCl_6$	Yellow	160° (d)	27.78	27.86	16.43	16.69	3.74	3.66
4.	bis-Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorozirconate.	$[(CH_3)_2N.C_6H_5.C_6H_7]_2.ZrCl_6$	White	215° (d)	29.75	29.30	12.60	12.54	3.70	3.84
5.	bis-Benzoylquinolinium hexachlorotitanate.	$(C_9H_7N.C_6H_5CO)_2.TiCl_6$	Greenish yellow	165-64°	28.29	29.21	6.72	6.57	3.92	3.84
6.	Benzoylquinolinium benzylhexachlorotitanate.	$(C_9H_7N.C_6H_5CO).C_6H_5CO.TiCl_6$	Light yellow	240-42°	33.78	35.38	7.84	7.98	2.51	2.33
7.	Di-quinoinostannic chloride hemibenzoyl chloride.	$(C_9H_7N)_2.SnCl_4.C_6H_5COCl$	Camel colour	89-91°	27.63	27.10	19.95	20.16	4.45	4.75
8.	Benzoylquinolinium pentachlorostannate.	$(C_9H_7N.C_6H_5CO).SnCl_5$	Yellowish white	97.5°	33.46	33.48	21.09	22.39	2.74	2.65
9.	Benzoylquinolinium pentachlorotellurite.	$(C_9H_7N.C_6H_5CO).TeCl_5$	Yellow	...	33.42	32.90	23.72	23.67	2.86	2.60
10.	Di-quinolinizirconium tetrachloride monobenzoyl chloride.	$(C_9H_7N)_2.ZrCl_4.C_6H_5COCl$	Chocolate	202-203°	28.08	28.09	14.20	14.44	4.94	4.43
11.	bis-Benzoylpyridinium hexachlorozirconate monobenzoyl chloride.	$(C_8H_5N.C_6H_5CO)_2.ZrCl_6.C_6H_5COCl$	White	300-10°	30.51	30.54	10.95	11.20	2.97	3.44
12.	Benzoylpyridinium benzylhexachlorozirconate.	$(C_8H_5N.C_6H_5CO).C_6H_5CO.ZrCl_6$	White	290-96°	35.84	35.99	15.46	15.38	2.66	2.36
13.	Benzoyl- α -picolinium benzylhexachlorozirconate.	$(C_8H_7N.C_6H_5CO).C_6H_5CO.ZrCl_6$	Light yellow	143-45°	35.12	35.09	15.08	15.03	2.54	2.30
14.	bis-Benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorostannate monobenzoyl chloride.	$(C_8H_5N.C_6H_5CO)_2.SnCl_6.C_6H_5COCl$	Reddish brown	70-72°	28.01	28.63	13.32	13.67	3.36	3.22
15.	bis-Benzoyl- β -picolinium hexachlorostannate.	$(C_8H_7N.C_6H_5CO)_2.SnCl_6$	Light yellow	101°	28.00	29.27	16.15	16.31	...	...
16.	β -picolinostannic chloride monobenzoyl chloride.	$(C_8H_7N)_2.SnCl_4.C_6H_5COCl$	Greenish yellow	...	29.71	30.20	16.16	16.03	4.67	4.76
17.	Di- β -picolinoflanium tetrachloride monobenzoyl chloride.	$(C_8H_7N)_2.TiCl_4.C_6H_5COCl$	Yellowish brown	175-90°	34.42	34.38	9.24	9.27	5.23	5.42
18.	Benzoylquinolinium hexachloroantimonate.	$(C_9H_7N.C_6H_5CO).SbCl_6$	Dull white	220-30°	37.94	37.41	21.43	21.41	2.59	2.46

N.B. : Melting points are uncorrected.

* It was produced by subjecting complex No. 15 to vacuum.

(d) denotes decomposition.

Titanium tetrachloride forms a monosolvate with benzoyl chloride (Cullinane, Chard and Leyshon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4106; Bertrand, *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1880, 33, 403; 1881, 34, 631) and produces conducting solutions in it (Gutmann and Tannenberger, *Monatsh.*, 1957, 88, 216) which can be possible only if the monosolvate can give rise to ion pairs in solution.

The tetrachlorides of tin, tellurium and zirconium, however, do not give any solid solvates with benzoyl chloride (Part I, *loc. cit.*), but on the basis of analogy and the conductivity of their solutions (Gutmann and Tannenberger, *loc. cit.*), it can be imagined that they form solvates which ionise further as:

The strongly ionic metallic chlorides, which are expected to act as ansolvo-bases in benzoyl chloride, have been found to be insoluble in it; therefore dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride, which has a fair solubility in benzoyl chloride, has been used in their place. It reacts with the tetrachlorides of tin, titanium, tellurium and zirconium to furnish the normal salts, *bis*-dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorostannate, *bis*-dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorotitanate, *bis*-dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorotellurite and *bis*-dimethylphenylbenzylammonium hexachlorozirconate, which are insoluble in benzoyl chloride and separate out as fine crystalline powder. Their formation is represented by the following general equations:

It has been noted that in the case of stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride, these normal complexes are soluble in excess of the acid solutions and completely dissolve in benzoyl chloride when the acid/base molar ratio is 1:1. This can be due to the formation of the acid salts, which due to their very high solubility could not be isolated. Their existence, along with that of the normal salts, has been placed beyond doubt by carrying out conductometric titrations in benzoyl chloride (Johar, private communication). The formation of an acid salt can be represented as:

Organic tertiary bases form solvates with benzoyl chloride (Part I, *loc. cit.*) and furnish conducting solutions (Johar, *loc. cit.*). The ionisation of these solutions can be represented by

Quinoline forms two complexes with titanium tetrachloride, *i.e.*, the normal salt *bis*-benzoylquinolinium hexachlorotitanate and the acid salt benzoylquinolinium benzoylhexachlorotitanate. Formation of these can be represented by the general equation:

With stannic chloride also, quinoline affords two salts, the normal salt, *bis*-benzoylquinolinium hexachlorostannate and the acid salt, benzoylquinolinium benzoylhexachlorostannate, which have been isolated in their desolvated forms, diquinolinostannic chloride hemi-benzoyl chloride and benzoylquinolinium pentachlorostannate, which can be represented as follows:

Quinoline also reacts with the solvo-acid tellurium tetrachloride in benzoyl chloride to give rise to the acid salt, benzoylquinolinium benzoylhexachlorotellurite which has been isolated in a partly desolvated form as benzoylquinolinium pentachlorotellurite. Its complex with zirconium tetrachloride, diquinolinizirconium tetrachloride mono-benzoyl chloride, represents the formation and the desolvation of the normal salt, *bis*-benzoylquinolinium hexachlorozirconate,

Pyridine acts as a solvo-base like quinoline. With zirconium tetrachloride, which is a dibasic acid in benzoyl chloride, it gives both the normal salt, *bis*-benzoylpyridinium hexachlorozirconate, and the acid salt, benzoylpyridinium benzoylhexachlorozirconate. The former has been isolated in the solvated form:

Though no well-defined solvates of the tertiary bases, α -picoline and β -picoline, have been isolated (Paul and Singh, *Chem. Sci.*, 1957, 26, 391), yet the conductivity of their solutions (Johar, *loc. cit.*) leads one to conclude that these also will act as solvo-bases in benzoyl chloride as:

Equimolar quantities of α -picoline and zirconium tetrachloride react in their benzoyl chloride solutions to provide the acid salt, benzoyl- α -picolinium benzoylhexachlorozirconate. With stannic chloride, the normal salt, *bis*-benzoyl- α -picolinium hexachlorostannate, has been isolated in the solvated form by mixing together stannic chloride and α -picoline in the molar ratio of 1:2.

β -Picoline reacts with the solvo-acids, stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride, in benzoyl chloride solution, when mixed in a molar ratio of 2:1, to yield the normal salts, *bis*-benzoyl- β -picolinium hexachlorostannate and *bis*-benzoyl- β -picolinium hexachlorotitanate. The former under vacuum changes to di- β -picolinostannic chloride monobenzoyl chloride as:

and the latter has been isolated as di- β -picolinotitanium tetrachloride monobenzoylchloride:

The Lewis acid, antimony pentachloride, gives rise to a monosolvate with benzoyl chloride (Seel, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1943, 252, 24). Its formation and ionisation can be visualised as:

It will therefore act as a monobasic acid. The solvo-base, quinoline, reacts with the solvo-acid, antimony pentachloride, when mixed in the molar ratio of 1:1 in benzoyl chloride, to provide the normal salt, benzoylquinolinium hexachloroantimonate, formation of which is represented as:

EXPERIMENTAL

Purification of benzoyl chloride has already been described in Part I (*loc. cit.*). Stannic chloride and titanium tetrachloride were purified by treating them with pieces of tin and copper filings respectively and fractionating in an all-glass apparatus in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Tellurium tetrachloride was purified by resubliming. Zirconium tetrachloride (Johnson, Metthey & Co.) was available in pure state and was used as such. Antimony pentachloride was purified by distilling under reduced pressure. Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium chloride was recrystallised from lime-alcohol and the purity checked by analysis. Tertiary organic bases were kept over potassium hydroxide beads overnight and then fractionally distilled. The transfer of materials was carried out in a dry box, taking all precautions to expose them for the minimum of time.

Procedure.—For the preparation of the normal salts of the dibasic acids, the acid and the base were mixed in the molar ratio of 1:2. A previously cooled solution of the base in benzoyl chloride was placed in a conical flask, fitted with a calcium chloride guard tube and a dropping funnel containing a cold solution of the acid in benzoyl chloride. The acid solution was added dropwise to the base solution and the mixture thoroughly stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. A crystalline complex separated out with the evolution of heat in most of the cases. This was filtered in a dry atmosphere, washed successively with benzoyl chloride and dry petroleum ether (40-60°), dried under vacuum and analysed.

The same procedure was followed for the preparation of acid salts, with the difference that in this case the base solution was added dropwise to the cold solution of the acid and both the acid and the base were taken in equimolar quantities.

The estimation of nitrogen in the complexes was done, in most of the cases, in the Microanalytical Laboratory of Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford. In the case of a few complexes formed from tertiary organic bases, it was estimated by the Jackson and Smith method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 544).